

Predictions of toxicity of polar and nonpolar narcotic chemical mixtures using QSAR

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Abstract

Every day we are exposed to different chemicals of emerging concern through various products of domestic use, agricultural products, food products, industrial chemicals, and also through polluted water and air. These chemicals are present in the environment as a near-infinite number of chemical mixtures derived from numerous sources. Combined exposure to multiple chemicals can lead to adverse effects on human health or the ecosystem, even if single substances in the mixtures are below their individual safety thresholds. However, the current safety assessment protocols are primarily based on understanding the potential risk posed by single substances rather than their "real life" combinations; thus their potential combination effects might be overlooked. Risk assessment of chemical mixtures is a complex, laborious, and costly process due to the unending number of possible combinations. However, it has been an attractive domain of research for the scientific communities in the last 2 decades. To avoid ethical complications and other complexities, *in silico* techniques are now used for mixture's risk assessment. In the present study, quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models have been developed for the prediction of toxicity of mixtures of common polar and non-polar narcotic chemicals. The models have been developed using the pEC50 values (against *Photobacterium phosphoreum*) of 84 chemical mixtures as the endpoint. Only 2D structural invariants were used to derive the mixture descriptors in this study. We have employed the "Intelligent Consensus Predictor" tool available from http://teqip.jdvu.ac.in/QSAR_Tools/DTCLab/ with eight selected partial least squares (PLS) regression models based on their validation metric scores. It has been found out that an Intelligent Consensus model with external predictive variance (Q2F1) value 0.88 is the winner model which predicts the toxicity better than the individual models. Various descriptors such as- MLOGP2, SsNH2, N%, X5sol, B03[O-Cl], B05[O-Cl], T(N..Cl) are identified as important descriptors indicating the importance of the features like hydrophobicity, hydrogen bonding, polarity, and solvation parameters for mixture toxicity in this study. The developed models are able to efficiently predict the toxicity of polar mixtures, non-polar mixtures, and the combination of both also. Therefore, these models can be used for the risk assessment, prioritization, and data gap filling of polar and non-polar chemical mixtures.